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Sustainability Assessment Of Forestlands Along The Non-Tidal Reaches Of The Nun River Floodplains, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The fact that the principle of sustainability is highly recommended to be the main focus in all facets of human endeavors in all geographical units of the globe, this study is aimed at bringing to lime-light factors that are capable of impeding the sustainability qualities of forestlands along the Nun River floodplains of Bayelsa Sate, Nigeria. With the use of basic Socio-economic survey tools, as well as practical field observations and measurements, the study was able to identify: Traditional land tenure system. size of forestlands, multi- dimensional use of the forest resource, youth restiveness and, unstable government policies as basic factors that are capable of disrupting sustainable qualities of the forestlands in the study area. In its bid to improve on the qualities in the forestlands of the study area, this work has recommended for a thorough and practical professional enlightenment on the principle of sustainable development in the area, a re-visit to the constitution of the Big-Three Interrelationship' in terms of forest resource conservation, as well as a more diversified research approach in the management of forestlands of the study area.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Sustainability Assessment, forestlands.

INTRODUCTION

The terrestrial environment is one, out of the three major environments making up the biosphere. The biosphere is mainly made up of the life supporting parts of the atmospheric environment, aquatic environment and the terrestrial environment. The importance of each of these environments in terms of life-sustenance is almost equal. In other words, these three major aspects of the biosphere environment have a very strong interrelationship.

On the part of the terrestrial environment, vegetation is major. Equally, as touching vegetation, forest is major. The significance of the terrestrial environment to the globe cannot be overemphasized as regarding aesthetics, soil nutrient control, erosion-control, climate control and general human activities such as agriculture, settlements, housing, furniture, transportation etc. Interestingly, all of the stated areas of significance concerning the terrestrial environment, are the same with vegetation as well as, with forest (Aniah and Okpiliya, 2003).

Forests, being the tree-plant parts of the earth's surface have been discovered to exist at various forms (Waugh, 1995; Bellamy, 2007). Forests can exist on natural platform and on man-made platform. Naturally, forests are in various types including Tropical Evergreen Forest, Tropical Monsoon Forest, Coniferous Forest and so on. Basically in Nigeria, we have the tropical evergreen forest which is sub-divided into High Equatorial Forest or Rain Forest, Freshwater Swamp Forest and Saltwater Swamp Forest or the Mangrove Swamp Forest (Iloje, 2004).

While the significance of forests all over the globe is so enormous, the significance is more obvious in the developing countries which Nigeria is not an exception. Following this trend, the demonstration of this significance is quite practical along the Nun River catchment. The household, communal and public involvements in their diversified uses of forest and forest resources within the area is enough to cause reasonable concerns in conservation minded persons.

With the introduction of the principle of sustainable development in modern society, it becomes quite imperative for the application of basic professional assessment methods on the manner in which the forests within the catchment of the Nun River are being used. The Nun River, as major as it is, this study concentrates only on the non-tidal reaches. To have this perspective a practical achievement, this study has worked on the following objectives; To

1. Determine the forest size of the study area.
2. Identify the basic resources in the forest of the study area.
3. Identify the personalities involved in the use of the forests of the study area.
4. Examine the factors that are capable of impeding the sustainability qualities of forestlands along the Nun River floodplains.
5. Make reasonable recommendations for lasting solution.

THE PRINCIPLE OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AS A TOOL FOR EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF FORESTLANDS IN A RIVERINE ENVIRONMENT

Pearce and Atkinson (2010) have traced the origin of sustainable development to the economic growth theory of the 1970s. They opined that, what determines the ability of a given set of humans to improve their wellbeing is the quantity and quality of capital assets, in other words, wealth available at the time. Against this background, in 1987, the World Commission on Environment and Development (also known as the Brundtland Commission) defines sustainable development as the development that meets the needs of this present generation without compromising the abilities of the future generations to meet their own needs. In agreement with the forgoing, deductions from Nwafor (2006) and David-Clayton (1999) assert that, for development to be sustainable, it must take account of the socio-economic and ecological factors of the short-term advantages and disadvantages of alternative actions. To simply put, it is the use of resources at a rate which could be maintained without diminishing future levels, but development which also takes social implications into account.

In June, 1992, the Earth Summit held in Rio de Janeiro (a conference attended by representatives of 178 nations of the globe) looked for new ways to manage planet earth together and in harmony. The whole issue was the environment and the challenge was on how to avoid its destruction. According to Raven, Berg and Johnson (1993) in Eli (2012) the fear the Earth Summit had was, to never handover an unhealthy and poorly fed earth to the next generation. In line with this perspective, Raven, et al (1993) suggested for the application of sustainable development to agriculture as sustainable agriculture. According to them (ibid), that sustainable agriculture is also alternative agriculture which means, the type of farming that relies on beneficial biological processes and environment friendly chemicals.

Ukpong (2009) on his part is a bit sceptical about the possibility of implementing a world- wide acceptable sustainable development principle. That, since the publication of 'our common goal' by the Brundtland Commission in 1987, efforts have been made to develop common principles for sustainable development, but to no avail. This is because, the commission discovered a great difference in the countries' social and economic systems and differences in their ecological conditions. That, it would not be possible to determine a policy that is sustainable to all.

In 2006, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy, Macedonia, mapped out a strategy for sustainable development of forestry in the Republic of Macedonia. In the strategy, the ministry was able to state categorically that, for any nation to have its forest sustainable; it must first have general vision, goals and directions. Secondly, the forestry sector must be well stream-lined and structured, as well as the forestry resources and their economic issues. Thirdly, outlining clearly, the role of government in the development of the forestry sector with the goal of keeping it sustainable. Fourthly, making an obvious analysis of the interrelationship existing between forestry and environment; bearing in mind that biodiversity nature of the forests is well protected and sustained. Fifthly, the socio-economic impact of the forest should be well explained and nurtured; especially in the areas of employment creation, livelihood supplies, and poverty reduction. The sixth part of the mapped out strategy was its focus on transformation of the forestry strategy into action. i.e the strategy itself must have the ability for practical implementation.

In a related approach in 2016, the World Resources Institute came with a strategy to help the Belgian Government Procurement Policy in realizing sustainable forest management with the question 'Have forests been sustainably managed?' The Conclusion in the write-up was: yes, forests can be sustainably managed only if the economic, social and environmental interests are held in equal esteem. Such thematic and practical approaches are what regions and places in the globe need for sustainable forest management.

The vegetation making up the watershed of River Nun shows a peculiar importance in local and neighboring perspectives. Against this background, forestlands of the Nun River Valley are specifically

studied in their sustainability status and factors that are capable of delimiting the qualities of their sustainability are as well considered.

THE STUDY AREA

The non-tidal reaches of the Nun River are located in Bayelsa State. It extends from the bifurcation of the Niger River in the North of Bayelsa State to a point lower than Peremabiri in Sothern Ijaw Local Government Area, South of Bayelsa State. The non-tidal limits of the Nun River fluctuate between the dry season and wet season. The limits become so extensive toward the south at the peak of the floods in October. At the peak of the dry season, the non- tidal behaviour of the Nun moves a bit northwards, even above Oporoma to the reaches within Angiama and Oweikorogha.

River Nun has a length of up to 195Km (Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, 1980 and: Eli and Bariweni, 2017). Its floodplains are on both sides of the valley (i.e on both the eastern and western sides). To the east, it is bounded by the floodplains of the Taylor Creek, Epie Creek, Ekole Creek and River Sangana. To the west, it is bounded by the floodplains of Upper Forcados River, Sagbama Creek, Egbedi Creek, Ogobiri Creek and the Peliton River.

The floodplains of the Nun River are quite extensive, having a very rich vegetation highly influenced by the equatorial climate and a much humid riverine environment. In this respect, it has a high mix of plants of the saltwater swamps, freshwater swamps and much dotted equatorial high forest trees and climbers as well as divers fauna. In the midst of such a luxuriant biodiversity, the inhabitants are engaged in divers socio-economic activities.

Fig 1: Bayelsa State showing River Nun

Source: Cartography unit, Dept. of Geography and Environmental Management, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State

Fig 2: The Sampled settlements

Source: Cartography unit, Dept. of Geography and Environmental Management, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

From January 2025- May, 2025, the study followed to methodological perspectives of physical and socio-economic scales for the collection of field data. The physical perspective was mainly by direct measurements and observation, while the socio-economic perspective was by questionnaire and interviews.

The physical measurements and observations were carried out on the areas that are covered by natural vegetation (vis-vis forests) on the levees, backswamps and bluffs. With the help of 5 field assistants the following materials system (GPS), 10 ranging poles, 6 whistles, 6 lifejackets and one local canoe at each of the sampled settlement.

For the socio-economic survey, six communities were purposively selected along the upper reaches of River Nun i.e Odi, Kiama, Opokuma, Polaku, Gbaran-Toru and Agudama-Ekpetiama. Thirty household heads per community were randomly selected for questionnaire and personal interview administration, making up to One Hundred and Eighty (180) copies of questionnaire. See table 1

Table 1: Sampled communities and copies of questionnaire administered.

S/N	Name of Community	No of questionnaire	%
1.	Odi	30	16
2.	Kaiama	30	16.7
3.	Opokuma	30	16.7
4.	Polaku	30	16.7
5.	Gbaran-Toru	30	16.7
6.	Agudama-Epetiama	30	16.7
Total	6	180	100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following the methodological structure of the sampled reach of the River Nun and sampled communities i.e from the bifurcation to Agudama-Ekpetiama, and from Odi to Agudama-Ekpetiama respectively, the results from the fields are stated in the order below;

- i. Forest size of the study area (i.e the sampled area).
- ii. Basic resources in the forests of the study area.
- iii. Personalities involved in the use of the forests of the study area.
- iv. Factors that are capable of impeding the sustainability qualities of forestlands along the floodplains of the non-tidal reaches of the Nun.
- v.

1. THE FOREST SIZE OF THE STUDY AREA

With the use of a landscape map of Bayelsa State produced by the office of the Surveyor- General of the State in 2008, and by direct field observation and practical measurements at some specific points as confirmatory exercise, the floodplains and forest size of the study area were determined.

The floodplains of the Nun River have a total area of 1440Km². Out of this, with a length of about 75km, the study area (i.e from the bifurcation to Agudama-Ekpetiama) was determined to have a floodplain covering an area of 432km². See Fig. 3

Fig 3: The Floodplains of the Study Area.

Source: Cartography Unit, Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State.

Although, the entire floodplain was seen covered by vegetation, the luxuriant high equatorial forest spots were seen as narrow as 100-300meters, while a few of them were measuring close to 500metres wide. On the other hand, the bluffs were seen to be quite extensive (measuring up to 1-2 kilometres wide). The physical distortions by numerous extensive backswaps, lakes and natural waterlogged spots together with minor creeks and miniature rivers (as adopted from Mayhew, 2009) have retarded the actual extensiveness of the forestlands.

BASIC RESOURCES IN THE NUN RIVER FORESTLANDS

The basic resources discovered include; wood, palms/fibre, climbers, saprophytes, animals, insects, swamp fish, fruits, ferns, etc. see Table 2

Table 2: Basics Resources in the Nun River Forestlands

	Main Resource	Examples
1.	Plant Resources	i. Wood: (a) Hard wood: e.g Afaras, Mahogany, Iroko (b) Soft wood: e.g cotton-trees, flamboyant trees (c) Shrubs
		ii. Palms: (a) oil palm (b) Raffia palm
		iii. Others e.g climbers, ferns and saprophytes.
		iv. Fruits e.g Irvingia (bush mango)
2.	Animal Resources	i. Mammals ii. Reptiles and Amphibians: e.g Iguanas, Aligators, a few crocodiles etc. iii. Swamp-fish iv. Insects including honey bees

PERSONALITIES INVOLVED IN THE USE OF THE FORESTS OF THE STUDY AREA

With the presence of diversified resources in the forests as well as petroleum deposits in the study area, the inhabitants and people from all works of life including multi-national Companies and the Federal Government are attracted. See Table 3 for more details.

Table 3: Personalities Involved in the Use of The Forests of the Study Area

S/N	Personalities Involved in the use of the forests of the Study Area	Percentage (%)
1.	Inhabitants of the area;; including men. Women and youths.	20
2.	Strangers from other parts of Nigeria especially from the East 45 and West; for logging business, gathering of fruits c.g bush mango, and extraction of tree roots, leaves and stems for medicinal and domestic use.	45
3.	Multi-national companies: The basic ones involved are seismic 20 companies and the extraction companies. The major ones currently involved are United Geophysical, Nigeria Limited and Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), respectively.	20
4.	The Federal Government : this was discovered in the field to be a 15 case of indirect involvement i.e in the area of statutory rights given to these multi-national companies.	15
Total		100

With these many characters using the resources in the forests of the study area, it was discovered that the forests are haphazardly used on a daily basis. In table 3 above, the highest personality with the highest percentage (45%) is strangers from other parts of the country.

Further inquiries in the field revealed that the activities as stated in relationship with strangers from other parts of the country are increasing daily. They enter the forests themselves to carry out these activities.

FACTORS THAT ARE CAPABLE OF IMPEDING THE SUSTAINABILITY QUALITIES OF FORESTLANDS ALONG THE FLOODPLAINS OF THE NON-TIDAL REACHES OF THE NUN

Kormondy (2012) in his concepts of ecology asserts that sustainability status of any part of the ecological features of the earth must come from a collection of all necessary factors of natural and human endeavours. A related approach, is the interpretation of sustainable development and sustainability given by Singh (2014). He emphasises that the main aim of sustainable development is attainment of economic growth, environmental protection, and health and happiness. On these grounds, he opines that for any feature in the environment to exhibit sustainability qualities, it must demonstrate economic growth in the people concerned, environmental protection of the area and, must effect good health and happiness in the people concerned.

In the field, the forestlands along the Nun were assessed according to economic growth, environmental protection and, health and happiness giving qualities. Therefore, the following factors were discovered as impediments to the sustainability qualities of the forestlands: see Table 4 below.

Table 4: Factors Impeding Sustainability Qualities of Forestlands along the Nun River

S/N	Forest Sustainability Impediment-Factor	Percentage (%)
1.	Traditional land tenure system	30
2.	Size of the forestland	10
3.	Multi-dimensional use of the forest-resource	30
4.	Youth restiveness	5
5.	Unfavourable government policies	25
Total	5	100

Interestingly, the socio-economic survey employed in the field revealed that, out of the 5 major factors discovered in the field, traditional land tenure system and multi-dimensional use of the forests were the highest impediments (30% each) followed by the unfavourable government policies (25%), size of the forestlands (10%) and youth restiveness, the least impediment (with 5%).

Further inquiries on these findings revealed that, the traditional land tenure system as an impeding factor is so powerful because, land ownership in this study area is not under the control of community heads, but on family heads. This makes it so difficult for even the community administration to place orders against any ugly behaviour in the forest. Therefore, without due consultation, business people from any part of the country can make use of any part of the forest if permitted by the family head. Secondly, laws hardly hold firmly, if family heads are not in support.

The second highest impeding factor is the multi-dimensional use of the forest resource. Here, individual respondents complained bitterly about the diverse use of their forest and the fact that entry to their forests is free for all.

Unfavourable government policies were discovered occupying the second category of impediments. Personal interview with the inhabitants unveiled that, even the government (whether State or Federal) is not conscious about the indiscriminate use of the forests of the study area.

Youth restiveness was seen occupying the least. To support this, the personal observation and interview revealed that the illegal refinery system that is so common with youths of other areas, is not with youths of the study area.

Although, the size of the study area's forestlands was discovered verse enough, it was also seen as not a very serious impediment i.e next to the least. Inquiries in the field with the inhabitants revealed that size being small is not the problem, that what is important is the use of the forestland understandably and cohesively.

CONCLUSION

This study on sustainability assessment of forestlands along the non-tidal reaches of the Nun River floodplains in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, was actually carried out through socio-economic and direct physical measurement techniques. Although, the main focus was to discover major factors that are capable of impeding sustainability qualities in the forestlands along the Nun River floodplains. In the process of achieving this, the study also considered other related areas which it has discovered as follows;

- i. Forest size of the study area was discovered not verse enough in occupying the floodplains. The floodplain is also discovered to be extensively occupied by backswamps and other smaller creeks, lakes and waterlogged depressions.
- ii. Basic resources in the forestlands were discovered to be widely enormous i.e biodiversity of the forestlands is highly rich in both floral and faunal status.
- iii. Personalities involved in the use of the forests of the study area are wide-embracing, including; inhabitants, strangers from various parts of the country, multi-national oil companies of exploration and exploitation status, and the federal government.
- iv. The factors that are capable of impeding the sustainability qualities of the forestlands revealed in this study include; Traditional land tenure system, multi-dimensional use of the forest resource, unfavourable government policies, size of the forestlands and youth

Based on these findings, the work actually came to a conclusion that, until the impeding factors are properly looked into, the forestlands of the Nun River floodplains will continue to demonstrate unsustainability qualities. restiveness.

RECOMMENDATIONS

At the conclusion above, the work has made the following recommendations;

- i. There should be a thorough and practical professional enlightenment on the principle of sustainable development in the inhabitants of the area and the leadership of the state government.
- ii. The concept of the Big-Three Interrelationship has to be obviously re-visited and imbibed. The big-three concept in this context refers to the government, the locals (i.e indigenes) and the environment should be seen on equal status in decision making and implementation (Eli, 2012).

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